

Multi-domain Network Hypervisor for Abstraction and Control of OpenFlow-enabled Multi-tenant Multi-technology Transport Networks [Invited]

Ricard Vilalta, Raul Muñoz, Ramon Casellas, Ricardo Martinez, Shuping Peng, Reza Nejabati, Dimitra Simeonidou, Noboru Yoshikane, Takehiro Tsuritani, Itsuro Morita, Victor Lopez, Thomas Szyrkowicz, and Achim Autenrieth

Abstract—A virtualization architecture is presented for deploying multi-tenant virtual networks on top of multi-technology optical networks. A Multi-domain Network Hypervisor (MNH) and a Multi-domain SDN Orchestrator (MSO) are introduced with this purpose. The MNH provides an abstract view of each virtual network and enables its control to each independent customer SDN controller. The MNH is able to provide virtual networks across heterogeneous control domains (i.e., GMPLS and OpenFlow) and transport (i.e., Optical Packet Switching and Elastic Optical Networks) technologies. The MSO is responsible for providing the necessary end-to-end connectivity.

We have designed, implemented and experimentally evaluated the MNH and MSO in an international testbed across Spain, UK, Germany and Japan.

Index Terms—optical network virtualization; SDN orchestration; resource allocation algorithms; GMPLS/PCE; OpenFlow; OPS; EON.

I. INTRODUCTION

Transport networks might include different optical technologies, such as Flexi-grid DWDM or Optical Packet Switching (OPS). They also consist of different heterogeneous control technologies, such as OpenFlow (OF) or Generalized Multi-Protocol Label Switching (GMPLS) and Path Computation Element (PCE). These technologies enable flexible and dynamic networking but also create a multi-domain multi-technology network scenario which needs to support end-to-end service provisioning. Such a transport network scenario raises important challenges for efficient network control and operations.

It is in this context, where OPS technology might be seen as an appealing packet transport solution for offering Ethernet services within a data center [1]. Elastic Optical Networks (EON) are able to provide long-reach optical transport for data rates beyond 100Gb/s [2]. Thus, EON will provide the required flexible transport capacity at the backbone networks, while OPS switches, used for intra-DC connections,

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Ricard Vilalta, Raul Muñoz, Ramon Casellas, and Ricardo Martinez are with the Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, 08860 Castelldefels, Spain (e-mail: ricard.vilalta@cttc.es)

Shuping Peng, Reza Nejabati, and Dimitra Simeonidou are with the High-Performance Networks Group, University of Bristol, UK

Noboru Yoshikane, Takehiro Tsuritani, and Itsuro Morita are with KDDI R&D Laboratories Inc., 2-1-15 Ohara, Fujimino-shi, Saitama 356-8502, Japan

Victor Lopez is with Telefonica I+D, c/ Don Ramon de la Cruz 84, 28006, Madrid, Spain

Thomas Szyrkowicz and Achim Autenrieth are ADVA Optical Networking, Campus Martinsried, Fraunhoferstrae 9a, 82152 Martinsried/Munich, Germany

might provide the benefits of statistical multiplexing and connection-oriented packet-based services.

SDN orchestration has been introduced in order to support end-to-end connectivity by orchestrating the different network domains through per-domain SDN/OF or GMPLS/PCE controllers [3]. SDN orchestration takes into account the heterogeneous underlying network resources (e.g., multi-domain, multi-layer and multi-control). We have recently proposed the usage of a Multi-domain SDN Orchestrator (MSO) in order to support the need for end-to-end connectivity [4].

Optical network virtualization enables physical infrastructure providers to partition, abstract and compose their physical resources into multiple independent slices (i.e., virtual networks) with each virtual resource resulting in the same functionality of the real physical resource, with an acceptable performance penalty [5].

In the presented multi-layer multi-domain network scenario, there is the need for an SDN-enabled virtualization platform that allows abstracting and controlling a multi-domain multi-technology transport networks. The proposed virtualization layer will enable rapid deployment of applications and network services and improve overall network operations. The creation and operation of multi-tenant virtual networks also might increase network utilization. The proposed virtualization layer will also need to leverage the proposed solutions for SDN orchestration, by interacting with the MSO.

In an optical network supporting network virtualization, each Virtual Optical Network (VON) requires a control plane for the provisioning of dynamic, adaptive and fault-tolerant network services. Two control plane architectures are active subjects of research, namely GMPLS and OpenFlow (OF). On one hand, the GMPLS architecture is based on a distributed control plane (i.e., signaling, routing and link management), and has been extended to support delegating the path computation function to a path computation element (PCE) [6]. The Active Stateful PCE (AS-PCE) can receive the right of managing the active paths controlled by the nodes, allowing the PCE to initiate, modify or tear-down the connections established in the data plane. On the other hand, OF allows operators to control the network using software running on a logically centralized controller [7]. OF defines an open protocol that allows configuring a network device remotely.

This paper extends the work done in [8], which introduced a Multi-domain Network Hypervisor (MNH). The MNH allows the deployment of OF-enabled multi-tenant VONs across a multi-domain multi-technology transport infrastructure with heterogeneous control plane technologies. Once a requested VON is deployed, it is controlled by a Customer

Fig. 1. Per-domain Network Virtualization architecture

Fig. 2. End-to-end Multi-domain Network Virtualization architecture

SDN Controller (CSC). The MNH is responsible for:

- the interaction with an MSO for the deployment of the necessary multi-domain connectivity,
- the provision of a virtual network by providing the abstracted network view to its customer (i.e., tenant) SDN controller,
- the translation of the issued OF commands from the customer SDN controller to the necessary actions in the multi-domain network including the interaction with the MSO.

This paper is organized as follows: firstly, the different architectural approaches for a multi-domain virtualization are presented; secondly, the architecture of the MNH is presented; thirdly, the architecture of the MSO is discussed. Finally, we present the experimental assessment of the proposed MNH and MSO. Finally, we conclude the paper.

II. OPTICAL NETWORK VIRTUALIZATION

Optical Network Virtualization has been respectively studied in a single GMPLS-controlled domain [9] and an OF domain [10]. In addition, the provision of a multi-domain Virtual Optical Network (VON) has also been proposed with the usage of per-domain virtualization [9]. A Network Or-

chestrator (NO) was introduced in order to provision end-to-end connectivity within a multi-domain VON.

While IT resources can be easily virtualized, the provisioning of a VON for DC interconnection remains a research challenge, due to the fact that a DC interconnection usually comprises heterogeneous optical transport and control plane technologies, which do not naturally inter-operate. The authors in [11] have proposed virtual optical network services across multiple domains, but the work did not take into account the inherent heterogeneousness of multiple control domains.

[9] has proposed a multi-domain resource broker which takes into account this heterogeneity. Also an orchestration mechanism is presented, which allows the composition of end-to-end virtual transport infrastructures across different transport technologies as well as end-to-end network service provisioning across multiple VONs comprising different transport and control plane technologies.

Figure 1 provides an architectural view of the proposed per-domain virtualization. It can be observed how each domain is virtualized with a per-domain network hypervisor. The NO is introduced later in order to provide end-to-end services over the virtualized domains of a single multi-domain VON.

Another possible approach, which is proposed by the authors in this paper, is to provide end-to-end virtualization. The MNH acts as a network hypervisor to deploy multi-tenant VONs and allow their own individual customized control. The MNH runs over a network orchestrator, as shown in Figure 2. The network orchestrator is responsible for providing end-to-end connectivity on top of multi-technology transport networks. Although several functions might be shared between the MNH and the MSO (e.g., topology info, management), their objectives differ, so these can be considered two independent logical entities. Considering this approach, the MNH is in-line with the ACTN framework (IETF) [12] and the SDN architecture (ONF) [13], where hierarchical SDN controllers have been considered to provide different layers of abstraction.

III. MULTI-DOMAIN NETWORK HYPERVISOR SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Figure 3 shows the proposed MNH system architecture. Three hierarchical control levels are identified:

- Customer SDN Controller (CSC). A CSC is a SDN controller run by a VON customer for controlling its deployed VON.
- MNH and MSO are the central components of the virtualization architecture.
- Physical SDN Controller (PSC), which is the centralized instance in charge of a physical infrastructure (i.e., SDN controller).

The MNH is responsible for receiving VON requests, processing them and allocating physical resources. Moreover, the MNH maps between the allocated physical resources and the abstracted resources that are offered to the CSCs, and it controls such abstract networks, acting as a proxy for the OF protocol between a CSC and the underlying Physical Controllers. The partitioning of the resources is performed by the MNH, and to this end, the proposed system architecture relies on the MSO, which provides a generic

Fig. 3. Multi-domain Network Hypervisor System Architecture

network abstraction mechanism for the different transport infrastructure resources (e.g., OPS, flexi-grid).

Each tenant is able to request a VON. Once the VON has been correctly setup, the CSC acts as a standard SDN controller where the controlled VON is an abstracted slice of the different allocated physical resources, which are managed by its corresponding PSC.

The MNH architecture is as follows. The VON Controller is the component that is responsible for providing the MNH with an interface to request virtual switches and virtual links to deploy a VON. To do so, also the IP address of the CSC is necessary, so that the Virtual Switch Handler is able to provide an abstract network view of the allocated VON to the CSC. A virtual switch request includes the related physical domains and a number of virtual Ethernet ports. A virtual link request includes the source and destination virtual switches. The Resource Allocation (RA) component is responsible for the allocation of the physical ports of the physical domains to the virtual switches and requesting the

necessary multi-domain connections from the MSO (through the provisioning component) in order to interconnect the requested virtual switches, which are related to physical domains. Once the connections have been established, the RA allocates the virtual port identifiers, to which the connections are related.

For each VON, the Virtual Switch Handler establishes the necessary OF datapaths with the provided IP address of the corresponding CSC. Each OF datapath is provided by an emulated OF virtual switch. The different emulated OF virtual switches are interconnected with virtual links, so when the CSC triggers the topology discovery mechanism by means of Link Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP) to the emulated virtual switches, it is able to recover the VON topology. The emulated virtual OF switches are connected to the Virtual to Physical (V2P) Interpreter, which is responsible for translating the received OF command (e.g., FLOW_MOD) from the CSC using the abstract VON topological view, to the allocated physical resources. To this end, it consults the VON

Database for the allocated physical ports and the established LSPs. The processed requests are sent to the provisioning module, which is responsible for requesting the provisioning of the physical resources from the MSO.

Different protocols between the MNH and MSO might be expected. In this paper, we propose the usage of REST API as a NorthBound Interface (NBI) of the MSO. The MSO shall implement two basic REST API: service provisioning and topology request. Another possible solution for the MSO NBI might be the newly proposed Control Orchestration Protocol [14], which aims to abstract a common set of control plane functions used by an various SDN controllers, allowing the interworking of heterogeneous control plane paradigms (i.e., OpenFlow, GMPLS/PCE).

It is important to analyze the scalability of the proposed architecture. The MNH can be implemented as a single logical entity which might be running on several servers. Due to its ability to offer abstracted and virtual networks, several MNH can be considered in a hierarchical deployment in order to absorb the growth of different underlying network domains.

IV. MULTI-DOMAIN SDN ORCHESTRATOR SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The MSO is introduced in order to support end-to-end connectivity by orchestrating the different network domains through per-domain SDN/OpenFlow or GMPLS/PCE controllers. The MSO must take into account the heterogeneous underlying network resources (e.g., multi-domain, multi-layer and multi-control).

The MSO (Fig. 3) architecture is based on the proposed Application-based Network Operations (ABNO) [15], and has been validated for multi-layer multi-domain network orchestration in [16] and [4]. The Network Orchestration Controller is the component responsible for handling all the processes involved and to provision end-to-end connectivity services.

The Topology Manager is the component of the MSO which is responsible for gathering the network topology from each control domain and building the whole network topology which is stored in the Traffic Engineering Database (TED). The TED includes all the information about network links and nodes, and is used by the dedicated PCE for calculating routes across the network.

The Virtual Network Topology Manager (VNTM) is responsible for the multi-layer management. In the proposed architecture, the VNTM arranges the establishment of an optical connection, which is then offered as a logical L2 link to satisfy an incoming L2 connectivity demand.

The Provisioning Manager implements different provisioning interfaces to command the forwarding rules and the establishment of connectivity segments into the data plane. The Flow server stores the connections established in the network into a Flow DataBase (FlowDB). The NBI of a Physical SDN Controller (PSC) is typically technology and vendor dependent, so the MSO shall implement different PSC plugins for each of the NBI. It is assumed that the PSCs are able to provide network topology information and flow programming functions.

In the proposed MNH and MSO architecture, VON resource allocation is introduced in two steps. Firstly, virtual switch resources are assigned by the RA component of the

MNH. Secondly, the RA is responsible for requesting the multi-domain connections to the MSO. These multi-domain connections will be offered as virtual links. The MSO PCE component is the responsible to compute the allocation of the requests of multi-domain connections, which will later be offered as virtual links to the MNH. The algorithm run in the PCE during the proposed experimental setup is described in [4].

In our testbed, both the Provisioning Manager and the Topology Manager are connected to OpenDayLight (ODL) and AS-PCE, through their specific plugins. ODL is responsible for the OF domains through the ODL REST API, and the AS-PCE initiates the establishment of connections into the GMPLS-based DWDM optical network using the PCEP.

V. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

To experimentally validate the proposed MNH architecture, Figure 4 shows the MSO view of the experimental scenario. The MSO topology consists of four OPS domains (KDDI R&D Labs), two OPS/OCS domains (both provided by University of Bristol), and two OCS domains (provided by CTTC and ADVA). Each physical domain has been abstracted as a node, following the previous work on the MSO [4]. Two different VONs are requested. Figures 5-6 show the different CSC1 and CSC2 views.

In Figures 5-6, the relationship between the virtual Ethernet switches and links (for VON1 and VON2) and the physical domains is provided, including OPS Labels (e.g., A:1/L:109 indicates Domain A Port 1 OPS label out: 109) of the established connections.

The workflow to deploy and control VON1 is detailed in Figure 7. In this workflow, Customer 1 is responsible for triggering the deployment of VON1. Customer 1 issues a request to the MNH, which requests the necessary multi-domain connectivity for deploying VON1 from MSO. In the presented scenario, two bidirectional multi-domain connections are requested: A-G, A-I.

The connections are established by MSO, which provides the port interfaces and the assigned labels (A:1/L:109-G:1/L:110 and A:1/L:111-I:1/L:112). The procedure followed by the MSO has been previously detailed in [4]. Once the necessary connections have been established and the physical network resources have been allocated and mapped to abstract resources, the MNH creates the OF-enabled VON1. Finally, the MNH notifies Customer 1.

Once VON1 has been deployed, Customer 1 can connect CSC1 (e.g., using ODL) to MNH in order to control it. CSC1 and MNH start the different virtual OF switches with their datapaths for VON1, following standard OF 1.0 protocol. CSC1 can also trigger a topology discovery protocol (i.e., LLDP) to discover VON1 topology. If CSC1 triggers an OF command to a virtual OF switch, the MNH receives the OF command and translates it to the necessary actions to be performed by the MSO.

For example a `FLOW_MOD` command with match (virtual switch 5, input port 10) action (output port 51), it is translated to an instruction to the MSO to interconnect the ports 2 and 1 of physical domain A, with labels 0109. Once this action is processed by the MSO, the MNH sends a `FLOW_MOD` acknowledgment to CSC1.

If the assigned connections for the virtual links in VON2 are analyzed, it can be observed that VON1 and VON2 share

Fig. 4. Multi-layer multi-domain network scenario

Fig. 5. Customer SDN Controller 1 VON1 topological view

Fig. 6. Customer SDN Controller 2 VON2 topological view

control domains, so multi-tenancy is applied. For example, the virtual port 1:71 is mapped to A:1/L:113-I:1/L:114.

We have developed a proof-of-concept prototype of the MNH, which sits on top of the MSO of the international testbed of the STRAUSS project as shown in Figure 3, in order to experimentally assess the multi-tenant transport network virtualization across multiple heterogeneous SDN/OpenFlow and GMPLS/PCE domains.

The experimental assessment is performed at the control

Fig. 7. Multi-domain Network Hypervisor workflow

plane level (i.e., no hardware configuration is performed at the domains). Each domain's PSC is connected to the MNH and MSO through OpenVPN. Eight domains are involved in the experiment: four OF-controlled OPS domains from KDDI R&D Labs, two OF-controlled OPS/OCS domains from BRISTOL, a GMPLS-controlled OCS domain with active stateful PCE from CTTC and an OF-controlled domain from ADVA, as shown in the network topology in Figure 4.

The MNH has been implemented using the virtual switch of POX. The different MNH components have been implemented as POX components and a REST API has been provided. The implementation of the MSO has been previously reported in [17] and uses Python for most of the components and C++ for the PCE component. Several internal REST interfaces are offered between the different components.

Figure 8 shows the captured messages for VON1 deployment and control. Firstly, we observe the different connection requests from MNH (10.0.34.14/84.88.61.59) to MSO (10.0.34.14). Once the VON1 network resources have been allocated, the communication between the CSC1 (10.1.1.106) and MNH is established by means of OF protocol. Secondly, when VON1 has been deployed and CSC1 issues an OF command (see Figure 9), we observe how this command is processed by the MNH, an action is requested to MSO and

Phase	Source	Destination	Protocol	Message
VON 1 deployment	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	250 GET /get_topology HTTP/1.1
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	1596 HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	291 POST /set_flow HTTP/1.1
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	306 HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	291 POST /set_flow HTTP/1.1
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	306 HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	291 POST /set_flow HTTP/1.1
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	306 HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	291 POST /set_flow HTTP/1.1
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	306 HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)
VON 1 control	84.88.61.59	10.1.1.106	OFP	76 Hello (SM) (8B)
	10.1.1.106	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Features Request (CSM) (8B)
	10.1.1.106	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Features Request (CSM) (8B)
	10.1.1.106	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Features Request (CSM) (8B)
	84.88.61.59	10.1.1.106	OFP	244 Features Reply (CSM) (176B)
	84.88.61.59	10.1.1.106	OFP	292 Features Reply (CSM) (224B)
	10.1.1.106	84.88.61.59	OFP	148 Flow Mod. (CSM) (88B)
	10.1.1.106	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Barrier Request (CSM) (8B)
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	358 POST /set_flow HTTP/1.1
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	306 HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)

Fig. 8. Wireshark capture of VON1 deployment and control

```

▼ OpenFlow Protocol
  ▼ Header
    Version: 0x01
    Type: Flow Mod (CSM) (14)
    Length: 80
    Transaction ID: 31090515
  ▼ Flow Modification
    ▼ Match
      ► Match Types
        Input Port: 10
  
```

Fig. 9. OpenFlow FLOW MOD command between CSC1 and MNH (detail of Fig. 8)

Phase	Source	Destination	Protocol	Message
VON 2 deployment	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	291 POST /set_flow HTTP/1.1
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	306 HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)
	10.0.34.14	10.0.34.14	HTTP	291 POST /set_flow HTTP/1.1
VON 2 control	10.1.1.107	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Hello (SM) (8B)
	10.1.1.107	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Hello (SM) (8B)
	84.88.61.59	10.1.1.107	OFP	76 Hello (SM) (8B)
	84.88.61.59	10.1.1.107	OFP	76 Hello (SM) (8B)
	10.1.1.107	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Features Request (CSM) (8B)
	10.1.1.107	84.88.61.59	OFP	76 Features Request (CSM) (8B)
	84.88.61.59	10.1.1.107	OFP	244 Features Reply (CSM) (176B)
	84.88.61.59	10.1.1.107	OFP	244 Features Reply (CSM) (176B)

Fig. 10. Wireshark capture of VON2 deployment

TABLE I
SYSTEM SETUP DELAYS

	VON prov. delay	VON prov. delay overhead	VON overhead control delay
VON 1	10.74s	26ms	38ms
VON 2	5.78s	7ms	27ms

finally the OF command is acknowledged to CSC1.

The messages captured by wireshark for VON2 deployment are shown in Figure 10. The message exchange between the MNH and MSO relates to the necessary establishment of connections for the virtual link provisioning. Later CSC2 (10.1.1.107) connects to MNH in order to control the deployed VON2.

The measurements for the deployment and control of VON1 and VON2 are shown in Table I.

To measure the average VON provisioning delay, ten measurements were taken for each VON provisioning. The VON provisioning delay is in average around 10.7s and 5.7s for VON1 and VON2, respectively. These values take into account the necessary time to recover the topology of each

underlying domain, the inter-domain and intra-domain path computation time and finally the setup delay of the necessary connections. The difference in the VON provisioning delay between VON1 and VON2 can be explained with the different number of virtual links that need to be established.

We have defined the VON provisioning delay overhead as the required time for the MNH to set up a virtual OF VON, which is in the order of milliseconds.

Finally, the VON control delay overhead is the delay introduced by the OF commands translation process at the MNH, which is also in the order of milliseconds.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have presented and experimentally assessed a Multi-domain Network Hypervisor that can dynamically deploy and control multi-tenant VONs on top of a multi-domain multi-technology transport network, with the support of a Multi-domain SDN Orchestrator. A customer can directly manage and control its own deployed VON with its own SDN controller, through the usage of OpenFlow protocol.

The proposed architecture has been validated over an international testbed across Spain, UK, Germany and Japan. The obtained results show the low overhead introduced by the MNH in terms of provisioning delay or control delay.

These results indicate that the solution provided in this paper, that is, MNH and MSO, is a feasible and powerful solution that can support the scalability of the multi-tenant virtual network control over multi-technology transport network domains.

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